

Japanese Figures in the Video Game Industry: Hideo Kojima (II)

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Hello, readers. After a period during which I could not devote time to Mr Kojima due to work commitments, I can finally offer you the second part of my article on the Japanese creative, recently honoured for his career at the Brazil Game Show at the time of writing this article —2017—. Without further ado, I shall continue exactly where I left off previously: after the release of *Metal Gear Solid* —1998. As I mentioned in the earlier article on Hideo Kojima, readers should be warned that significant plot elements from several video games will be revealed. Following this entry, a third and final article was published, covering some of Hideo Kojima’s projects up to the present day.

The New Millennium: *Metal Gear Solid 2: Sons of Liberty* and Kojima’s Other Franchises

In 2001, Konami released the next instalment of the *Metal Gear* series, *Metal Gear Solid 2: Sons of Liberty*. In this video game, which was advertised everywhere and whose trailers made it clear, the protagonist was initially to return as Solid Snake... Until players finally experienced the game at home, revealing that, after the prologue, the true protagonist would be Raiden, not Snake.

The game begins in 2007. A cargo ship navigates the Hudson River in New York, and the title opens with a mysterious figure walking across a bridge... The enigmatic individual is none other than Solid Snake, who, after dropping his cigarette, prepares to board the cargo ship in one of the most memorable introductory sequences for video game enthusiasts.

Metal Gear Solid 2 was a pioneering title in demonstrating lip-sync on characters' faces and in incorporating high-quality animations for its time, achieved through motion capture. Snake now works alongside Hal Emmerich in the organisation Philanthropy, which he established together with Otacon and Mei Ling, specialising in the deactivation and sabotage of future projects involving weapons such as the Metal Gear bipedal vehicles.

Snake's mission in this prologue is to gather evidence regarding the construction of a new Metal Gear bipedal tank called Ray. Solid Snake successfully infiltrates the ship, confronting a mercenary group led by Sergei Gurlukovich and his daughter Olga, and obtains photographs that incriminate the United States Marine Corps. Suddenly, Revolver Ocelot appears, seizes the weapon, and causes the cargo ship to sink. Although Ocelot was part of Gurlukovich's mercenary team, he shoots both Sergei and the marine commander Scott Dolph before fleeing with the bipedal weapon.

Years later, in 2009, the true protagonist of this instalment, Raiden, enters the scene, with an introduction very similar to Solid Snake's in *Metal Gear Solid*. He is equipped with diving gear that conceals his face, and Colonel Campbell even refers to him as Snake at the start of his mission. Raiden's objective is to locate and rescue a series of hostages, among whom is the President of the United States. The hostages are being held in a decontamination facility called Big Shell, situated approximately 30 kilometres off the coast of Manhattan, in the open sea.

Raiden, the protagonist of most of the narrative of *Metal Gear Solid 2: Sons of Liberty*

In this mission, Raiden confronts a terrorist group known as the Sons of Liberty, whose leader claims to be none other than Solid Snake himself. The group Dead Cell provides support to the terrorists, who intend to destroy Big Shell, thereby causing a devastating ecological disaster. A team of United States Navy SEAL special forces has also infiltrated the facility, but all of them are killed by Dead Cell except for two members, Peter Stillman and Iroquois Pliskin.

Both assist Raiden in deactivating several bombs placed at strategic points by the character Fatman, one of Dead Cell's members and an explosives expert. It is later revealed that Fatman had once been a student of Peter Stillman before becoming a terrorist, a fact that has tormented the veteran bomb disposal specialist for years. Stillman is also haunted by a previous failure to defuse a bomb in a church, an incident after which he even pretended to be injured in order to avoid public disgrace. Stillman ultimately falls into one of Fatman's explosive traps and sacrifices his life in order to prevent a greater catastrophe, warning Raiden and Pliskin that another similar bomb had been placed elsewhere in Big Shell. Thanks to this warning, Raiden manages to prevent Big Shell from sinking.

Pliskin and Raiden eventually locate the hostages, and while they are planning to evacuate them safely with the assistance of a helicopter, the leader of the Sons of Liberty appears. Pliskin assists Raiden in the confrontation that follows, which ends when the leader escapes with the aid of Metal Gear Ray. Pliskin then reveals that he is in fact the real Solid Snake—with none other than Otacon acting as his pilot—. Together they discover that Big Shell was in reality being used as a cover to conceal Metal Gear Ray.

It is in this video game that the narrative of *Metal Gear* begins to grow considerably more complex. With the help of the President of the United States, James Johnson, Raiden discovers that democracy is not truly being applied, and that the country is secretly being controlled by a clandestine organisation known as the Patriots.

Raiden also learns that the leader of the Sons of Liberty is in fact Solidus Snake, a perfect clone of Big Boss—and therefore the “brother” of Solid and Liquid Snake—who, under the identity of George Sears, had previously served as President of the United States. Solidus rebelled against the Patriots and formed the terrorist group in order to escape their control, after falling from favour with the organisation following the failure at Shadow Moses, the incident in which Solid Snake thwarted the organisation's plans.

Solidus Snake, leader of the Sons of Liberty. Another of Big Boss's clones, whose resemblance to him becomes even greater when, during the course of *Metal Gear Solid 2*, he loses an eye.

Big Shell conceals what is known as Arsenal Gear, where an artificial intelligence employed by the Patriots to control information is hidden.

Ocelot executes the President of the United States, and Raiden attempts to reach the core of Arsenal Gear in order to destroy it. It is then that Raiden meets Emma Emmerich, an engineer and specialist in artificial intelligence, who plans to assist him in destroying the Patriots' AI, known as GW. Emma turns out to be Otacon's stepsister, as well as the computer scientist responsible for the "mind" behind GW. She is also the one who secretly developed a virus capable of destroying it should the need arise.

Raiden manages to rescue Emma, even diving while carrying her through a flooded section of Big Shell —Emma cannot swim, as she is traumatised by the death of her father, who drowned in a swimming pool when she was a child—.

E.E. —as Otacon calls his stepsister— is wounded by Vamp, one of the members of Dead Cell, and her injuries prove fatal. The farewell between Otacon and his stepsister becomes one of the most emotional scenes in the saga. Emma had long hated her brother for failing to come to the rescue of her stepfather —in reality Otacon's father, Huey— and for subsequently leaving home. Emma ultimately reconciles with her stepbrother, and Otacon, devastated, cannot forgive Vamp for what he has done, receiving the support of Snake, now his comrade and friend. Vamp is apparently defeated during his confrontation with the protagonists.

This scene is an excellent demonstration of how the character of Otacon has evolved from the classic secondary character of the scientist imprisoned in an enemy base into a strong man whose mission is now the most important thing to him.

Image from the scene of Emma Emmerich's death

Following this sequence, Otacon manages to escape from Big Shell with the hostages, but Raiden is captured by Olga Gurlukovich, who had become the leader of Gurlukovich's remaining mercenaries. Shortly afterwards, Raiden finds himself in a torture chamber, where Solidus Snake reminds him of his childhood as a child soldier during the Liberian Civil War —1987/1997—, during which Solidus had acted as his mentor. Solidus reveals to Raiden that he has in fact been an agent of the Patriots all along without even knowing it. After Solidus leaves the scene, Olga contacts Raiden and frees him from his captivity, explaining that she had been blackmailed in order to protect her daughter.

Olga had also been posing as Mr X, a false identity which, together with a cyborg ninja suit, she used to assist Raiden throughout the adventure. Later, Olga gives Raiden a sword, and in subsequent instalments he would assume the role of the cybernetic ninja so characteristic of the series. Solid Snake had allowed Raiden to be captured in order to reach Arsenal Gear himself, taking advantage of the fact that his enemies would be occupied with Raiden.

During his escape, Raiden finds himself naked and without equipment, and Colonel Campbell contacts him repeatedly, behaving and speaking in a completely absurd and erratic manner. It is later revealed, thanks to Otacon's investigations, that Colonel Roy Campbell is actually retired, and that Raiden had in fact been speaking to a programme created by the artificial intelligence GW, which had been impersonating the colonel. Rosemary herself, Raiden's girlfriend, had been assisting him during the mission as his support operator, and she reveals to Raiden that she is pregnant, moments before the communication is abruptly cut off.

Raiden must then face dozens of Metal Gear Rays —it is revealed that Arsenal Gear also served as a platform for transporting them— while Solid Snake fights Fortune, one of the members of Dead Cell and the daughter of the commander murdered by Ocelot two years earlier, Scott Dolph. Olga is killed by Solidus while attempting to protect Raiden during this confrontation.

Ocelot finally reveals that he too is an agent of the Patriots, and that the entire Big Shell mission had been a recreation of the Shadow Moses incident —the setting of the events of *Metal Gear Solid*— designed to create another perfect soldier capable of matching Solid Snake and Big Boss: Raiden. Ocelot then appears to be possessed by the transplanted arm of Liquid Snake, with the personality of the former Foxhound leader taking control of him, and he reveals to the protagonists his intention of hunting down and destroying the Patriots, after which he boards the first Metal Gear Ray and escapes from the scene.

Ocelot before leaving Arsenal Gear with the Metal Gear Ray

Raiden then faces Solidus Snake in a final confrontation after Arsenal Gear runs aground on the coast of Manhattan, with both characters falling onto the roof of Federal Hall. Solidus reveals to Raiden his intention to kill him in order to use the nanomachines implanted in his body, which would allow him to locate the Patriots and assassinate them. After that, he plans to establish a nation free from their control, called Sons of Liberty, a name based on the organisation of the same name that rebelled against the British government during the era of the Thirteen Colonies in the United States.

The Patriots' AI then contacts Raiden, forcing him to kill Solidus if he wishes to protect the life of Olga's baby and that of his girlfriend Rosemary. After defeating Solidus, Raiden has a final conversation with Solid Snake, who tells him that he is finally free to rebuild his life and stop being a puppet, as Snake himself had once been years earlier. Raiden reunites with Rose, while Snake departs with Otacon to hunt down the Patriots—it is revealed that the founding members whose identities they had obtained thanks to Emma's virus disc were in fact all already dead—.

This video game reflects Kojima's team's concern about the state of digital society and the flow of information, with Raiden himself functioning as a reflection of the player. A novice agent whose design departs from the stereotype of the hardened man and perfect soldier, Raiden instead appears as a younger and physically less imposing character. Like the player, he seems to know almost nothing about what is happening around him, feeling like a puppet manipulated by forces far greater than himself.

The Patriots themselves can be interpreted as Kojima's reflection on the condition of contemporary society, in which virtually all information is filtered, censored, or categorised by large corporations. In this respect, the game anticipated by several years later developments such as the study of internet memes and the growing control over information exercised by large companies and the intelligence agencies of various countries. This reading has become even more striking in recent years with the rapid expansion of artificial intelligence, which has permeated almost every productive sector. Nor was this the first time Kojima anticipated social developments in his video games.

Snake himself, at the end of the game, speaks to Raiden about something resembling future social networks, years before the emergence of early platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, or MySpace.

Raiden examining his dog tags —the player can choose the character’s name and date of birth— during his conversation with Solid Snake at the conclusion of *Metal Gear Solid 2: Sons of Liberty*.

It is through the characters that the greatest twists in the franchise are revealed. Ocelot proves to be a far more complex villain than initially thought, having previously used Liquid to pursue the Patriots, even discarding his own comrade-in-arms, Sergei Gurlukovich. Olga is utilised for her combat skills and strong ideals, including her love for Russia and her daughter, ultimately meeting her demise. During the adventure, she assumes the role of a cyborg ninja, emulating Gray Fox as a guide for Solid Snake during the Shadow Moses mission.

Meanwhile, Solidus Snake embodies the figure of the antihero, beginning as the main antagonist of the adventure. Thanks to the revelations regarding his character, both the player and Raiden come to admire his desire to liberate the world from the Patriots’ control, despite his brutal methods. The game offers a wide variety of situations, improving the methods for navigating stages as well as the controls.

Enemy artificial intelligence was enhanced compared with previous entries, allowing them to detect the player by observing their shadow. Additionally, soldiers employ squad tactics, cooperating and coordinating to locate the player, and it is possible to manipulate the lighting to prevent detection —turning lights off to create shadows or taking advantage of existing dark areas. *Sons of Liberty* also places a strong emphasis on cinematic presentation, leveraging the advanced technology available at the time to deliver highly emotive and well-directed sequences for players. However, as we will see Kojima himself would later do in subsequent games, the saga lacks the grandiose finale that many had been expecting in its most recent instalment.

The game explores concerns about the environment and the impact of governmental control over the perception of history. As the entire mission is a simulation—a masquerade orchestrated by the Patriots—it addresses the “digitalisation” of military operations, creating simulations and games for soldiers and civilians alike, so that war seems distant and entertaining rather than truly horrific. Raiden functions as the player’s surrogate, suddenly confronted with a real-world problem.

In 2002, the game was re-released as *Metal Gear Solid 2: Substance*, including new cutscenes, additional missions—some allowing the player to control Snake—and a virtual reality mission pack, echoing those of the original *Metal Gear Solid*. Although these missions carry no weight in the main narrative, the addition of *The Document of Metal Gear Solid 2*, an interactive documentary showcasing the game’s development, is noteworthy.

In 2001, Kojima’s team also launched a new franchise, *Zone of the Enders*, a science-fiction series in which players pilot combat robots—mechas—. The story revolves around human mining colonies on Mars and Jupiter, extracting resources from locations such as Callisto. The colonists are viewed with suspicion by Earth’s authorities, who impose harsh taxes, leading the colonies to rebel.

Several factions exist within this setting, the most notable being BAHRAM, which seeks to seize control of combat suits—pilotable robots known as “Frames”—and introduces a superweapon named Aumaan, capable of destroying entire solar systems. The franchise comprises two main games, following the stories of two pilots: Leo in the first game, and Dingo Egret, the protagonist of the 2003 sequel, *The 2nd Runner*, battling against BAHRAM’s plans to utilise Aumaan. Following Hideo Kojima’s departure from Konami, a third entry and future projects in the series were cancelled, despite the franchise having already spawned two anime adaptations.

Image from *Zone of the Enders: The 2nd Runner*, HD version—high definition—, 2012.

Another franchise created by Kojima during this period was Boktai, which consisted of two releases for the Game Boy Advance and centred on a vampire hunter who wields a solar weapon to defeat his enemies. The series included two iterations —*The Sun is in Your Hand*, 2003, and *Solar Boy Django*, 2004—. Both games made use of the photometric sensor embedded in the cartridge, which meant that Django’s weapon could only function during daylight —detecting UV rays— forcing players to engage with the game during daytime hours or in environments illuminated with UV lamps. If the player’s weapon ran out of ammunition while not in sunlight or at night, they would have to avoid enemies, as the difficulty would increase considerably.

A team within Konami, together with the studio Silicon Knights, produced in 2004 a remake of *Metal Gear Solid* entitled *The Twin Snakes* for the GameCube, utilising the graphics engine of *Metal Gear Solid 2*, along with its new mechanics —such as first-person aiming— and incorporating the involvement of film director Ryūhei Kitamura, who directed the action sequences of the original *Metal Gear Solid* which were re-shot for this release.

In 2004, a new *Metal Gear* release for Sony’s portable console, the PSP, also appeared, titled *Metal Gear Acid*, a card-based strategy game with a completely original story, separate from the main *Metal Gear* continuity. The term ACID stood for “Active Command Intelligence Duel”. This was followed by a sequel in 2006, *Metal Gear Acid 2*.

Snake Eater: The Cold War and Big Boss’s Origins

Also released in 2004 was the next mainline entry in the series, *Metal Gear Solid 3: Snake Eater*, followed in 2005 by a new edition, *Subsistence*, which introduced extras such as a new third-person camera mode —the first time in the franchise that the camera was free rather than fixed—. It is considered one of the finest games in the series, as well as one of the best stealth games ever created, and received a remake in 2025 by Konami, *Metal Gear Solid Δ*, although Kojima was no longer part of the team.

This game transports players to 1964, in the Soviet Union, exploring the past and origins of Big Boss. The title serves as a tribute to classic films such as *The Guns of Navarone* (1961), *The Great Escape* (1963), and *Where Eagles Dare* (1968), as well as the literary and film franchise of James Bond, created by author Ian Fleming in 1953. All of these works belong to the war, suspense, and espionage genres, making Kojima’s decision to set this adventure in Big Boss’s formative years as a secret agent during the Cold War both deliberate and thematically resonant.

Kojima and his team interwove a cast of fictional characters —all protagonists and secondary characters in this game— with historical figures such as Nikita Khrushchev and Lyndon Baines Johnson, leaders of the Soviet Union and the United States, respectively. This approach ensured that the narrative remained a work of fiction, yet, without the elements of science fiction such as the supernatural abilities of the characters, it could plausibly fit within historical events.

Major Zero —Tom— and Dr Clarke —Paramedic—. The former, Snake’s superior in the FOX unit; the latter, Snake’s doctor and assistant during his missions in *Metal Gear Solid 3*.

Big Boss —at that time known as Jack, and later as Naked Snake— works for the special forces organisation FOX, led by David Oh, the Major Zero, and affiliated with the CIA. He is dispatched to the fictional region of Tselinoyarsk in Russia, set within a dense jungle, with the mission of locating and rescuing the scientist Nikolai Stepanovich Sokolov, a rocket expert wishing to defect from the Soviet Union. Jack must infiltrate alone and unarmed, which is why the Major —whose name changes from Tom to Zero, as he will be known throughout the saga— bestows upon him the codename “Naked Snake”. The original name, Tom, pays homage to *The Great Escape*, specifically one of the tunnels dug by the soldiers, as well as David Bowie’s album *Space Oddity* (1969), while Zero is inspired by his agent codename in the SAS and the MI6 naming convention —in which the head of the organisation is referred to as “M”, for example, in the James Bond novels— “O”, modified to “0” for the saga.

This game is set almost entirely in a semi-open world —with loading screens between areas and moderately sized zones—, in contrast to earlier entries in the series, which took place in urban environments or almost entirely indoors —excluding artificially constructed facilities such as Big Shell, which is built in the middle of the ocean. *Snake Eater* revolves around survival and infiltration tactics that do not rely on high-tech equipment, but on using the environment and various camouflage suits to avoid detection, hunting animals, and seizing enemy weapons, given the nature of the mission.

Snake must confront various enemies from the Russian army, including special forces led by a young Ocelot, who provides some of the series’ most memorable sequences, featuring several duels reminiscent of classic western cinema.

He also battles the Cobra Unit, a special forces group founded by his former mentor, The Joy/The Boss, whom Snake must face later in the game. The Cobra Unit consists of war veterans traumatised by their experiences —The Boss herself being a World War II veteran— each embodying extreme emotions encountered in combat, reflected in their codenames.

The End —representing “the end”, an elderly sniper—, The Fury —“the fury”, attacking with fire—, The Pain —“the pain”, who uses a horde of killer bees to pursue Snake—, and finally, The Fear —“the fear” experienced by a soldier during battle, who confronts Snake with a potent toxin—. Snake also faces the Cobra Unit in a dream sequence against The Sorrow —“the sorrow”— a former lover of The Boss, a Soviet spy whom the US government ordered The Boss to assassinate.

The End, the sniper, fought during the American Civil War, and can be defeated if the player refrains from playing the game for a week. On returning, he will have literally died of old age.

The Boss defects to the Soviet Union, disillusioned by the treatment she had received —her government forced her to assassinate her lover, followed orders that exposed her to radiation during nuclear tests in the Nevada desert, participated in a space programme that sacrificed her health, served as a heroine in the Second World War without recognition, and so on—. Snake discovers her defection after escaping with Sokolov, who is kidnapped by The Boss’s unit. She confronts Snake, revealing herself as an enemy, having collaborated with him throughout the mission and acted as his mentor —she never disclosed her feelings or intentions to Snake, leaving him feeling betrayed.

Snake is severely wounded after his battle with The Boss, who demonstrates her superiority in combat, defeats him, and sends him tumbling off a cliff. The Boss delivers two portable nuclear warheads to the main antagonist of this entry, Colonel Volgin, who immediately launches one of them against Russian territory in an attempt to provoke an open conflict between the United States and Russia.

After recovering, Snake is sent on a new mission: to eliminate his mentor, The Boss, thereby placing the blame on her and allowing the US government to prevent a full-scale war with the Soviet Union.

During his journey, Snake faces the Cobra Unit and Ocelot, and encounters the mysterious spy Eva, who appears to work for the Russians but is later revealed to also be allied with the Chinese government, while simultaneously assisting The Boss in protecting Snake. Eva's objective is to recover a microfilm containing the Legacy of the Philosophers, a secret organisation to which Volgin's father belonged, whose resources the Colonel plans to use against the government of Nikita Khrushchev in order to overthrow it and unleash a total war against the United States.

Snake is captured and tortured by Volgin —with Ocelot serving as his subordinate, from whom he learns torture techniques— and even loses an eye due to a shot fired by Ocelot at Eva, which Snake attempts to shield with his own body, resulting in the bullet striking his eye. Gradually, Ocelot comes to admire Snake after being taught lessons during their encounters in the game.

Indeed, he abandons semi-automatic pistols on Snake's advice, replacing his standard-issue sidearm first with a revolver, and later with two. Ocelot's transformation is also influenced by witnessing Snake and The Boss sacrifice themselves for their mission, alongside the growth of his hatred for Volgin as he commits atrocities, increasing his disloyalty towards the Colonel.

Snake ultimately faces Volgin on two occasions. The first is a hand-to-hand battle, in which the Colonel uses a supernatural ability to manipulate electricity and bullets; the second sees Volgin piloting a prototype vehicle, the Shagohod, developed by Sokolov, which would serve as a basis for future Metal Gear machines.

Following this confrontation comes the final duel with The Boss and Snake's ultimate confrontation with himself. It is one of the most memorable battles in video game history. Knowing that her former pupil has come to finish her, The Boss reveals all her concerns and motivations, conveying what she had always intended for her student. When the player defeats her, the game pauses until the user presses the trigger button; breaking the fourth wall and making the player feel as if it is they themselves who have taken The Boss's life.

After escaping the area, Snake engages in another confrontation with Ocelot aboard the plane in which Eva escapes —this encounter can be lost, tied, or won, and is based on a Russian roulette scenario played with Ocelot's two revolvers. Ocelot departs, leaving a bond of mutual respect between him and Snake, which, as we shall see, evolves years later into friendship.

Image of the duel between Snake and The Boss, at the moment when the player must press the trigger to finish her off.

At the end of the mission, Eva and Snake share a few moments together. Eva is the one who reveals to Snake the full truth behind the plot, including whom she was working for and the reasons behind some of The Boss's actions. Snake is then received by the President of the United States to be decorated for his mission, yet he is already broken inside—a narrative twist both original and deeply human, devised by Kojima for the character.

Snake is henceforth referred to as Big Boss at the conclusion of this game, becoming a hero for his country and having accomplished his mission, yet feeling betrayed by himself for having done so and by his nation for having played unfairly with him and The Boss. It is here that his transformation into the future antagonist seen in *Metal Gear* and *Metal Gear 2: Solid Snake* begins. Powerless, he weeps at The Boss's grave, being, as Eva tells him in her tape, along with herself, the only one who truly remembers who The Boss really was, and not as a monster who nearly triggered a world war. Years later, both Zero and Big Boss will interpret, each in their own way, The Boss's desire for a world in which humanity lives in peace and acts as one.

Metal Gear thus becomes the story of Big Boss's fall, and how he eventually passes the heroic mantle and protagonist role to Solid Snake in the chronologically later entries. In *Metal Gear Solid: Portable Ops* (2006) and *Metal Gear Solid: Peace Walker* (2010), we witness how Big Boss begins to form the concept of a nation of mercenary soldiers, independent from any state's ideals or political interests, aside from those pursued by themselves. Kojima created the character of The Boss in *Metal Gear Solid 3*, a figure beloved by fans, who appears as though she has always been part of the saga since 1987, given her well-developed character, and who also becomes a key motivator for both Big Boss and Major Zero.

The driving concern of these games continues to be the threat of nuclear weapons, and, beginning with *Metal Gear Solid 3: Snake Eater*, also the themes of patriotism, loyalty, and how countries manipulate ideals to compel a soldier to commit horrific acts that ultimately destroy him—continuing the franchise's long-standing critique of war.

Metal Gear Solid 4: The Final Mission of Solid Snake

Metal Gear Solid 4: Guns of the Patriots (2008) is the direct narrative continuation of *Metal Gear Solid 2: Sons of Liberty*. The entire title serves as Kojima's farewell to the character of Solid Snake, with everything we see and experience designed to make us feel as he does—tired, exhausted, and “old”.

Indeed, Solid—now also called Old Snake due to his aged appearance—is a genetically altered clone of Big Boss, engineered to die prematurely to prevent him escaping the Patriots' control, suffering from a genetic disorder of accelerated ageing. *Guns of the Patriots* is set in 2014, only five years after the Big Shell incident in *Metal Gear Solid 2*, and Snake now looks like a true elderly man.

The game opens with Snake hooded and dressed in militia gear over his infiltration suit, delivering a voice-over monologue about what war has become in the modern age. He explains that the world is plagued by conflicts conducted by private military forces—a clear nod to real-world incidents involving private military companies (PMCs), such as Blackwater, which killed seventeen civilians in 2007 during the Iraq War—where soldiers are biologically enhanced in the *Metal Gear* universe through nanomachines.

Snake, now living on a plane alongside Otacon and Olga's daughter—rescued by Raiden after the events of *Metal Gear Solid 2*—Sunny, is sent at the request of Colonel Roy Campbell—this time the real man, not an AI, who now works at the UN—to stop the leader of a military uprising. That leader is none other than Revolver Ocelot, who now calls himself Liquid Ocelot, after taking on the persona of Liquid.

Old Snake's Octocamo suit adapts its pigmentation to any surface the character is on, facilitating camouflage.

Ocelot plans to take control of the nanomachines that connect the senses of soldiers to each other, a computerised system known as the “Sons of the Patriots”, which he will rename “Guns of the Patriots”, in order to unleash chaos. Snake encounters Drebin 893, an arms dealer who has worked for the Patriots and injects him with new nanomachines allowing him to use the weapons employed by his enemies, which are coded to prevent unauthorised use. Drebin also injects Snake with a new version of FOXDIE, a virus that was designed to terminate the lives of those opposed to the Patriots, including Eva, Ocelot, and Naomi.

Snake is reunited with Meryl, now leader of her own unit, who provides support during his mission. He also encounters Dr Naomi Hunter once again, whom he met during the events of *Metal Gear Solid*, and who is forced to work for Ocelot due to her expertise with nanomachines. Naomi warns Snake that the FOXDIE virus, which previously killed Liquid, will mutate within six months, becoming hazardous to anyone, not only specific individuals.

All encounters with franchise characters, and all the challenges Snake faces—including the virus, his limited lifespan, and confrontations with the Beauty and the Beast unit, composed of war-traumatised women who have completely lost their sanity and evoke memories of past adversaries—take their toll on him, while also creating a strong nostalgic impact for players recalling bosses from earlier entries. Old Snake finally meets Eva, who has survived all these years, revealing to him that she is his biological mother, since Big Boss was cloned without his consent by Major Zero, and she had agreed to give birth to Liquid and Solid—whose real name she reveals as David.

The narrative of this game reshapes the story of Big Boss. After even confronting Ocelot in a one-on-one battle, each piloting one of the franchise’s iconic Metal Gears—Rex for Snake, controlled by the player, and Ray for Ocelot—and seeing how Raiden nearly loses his life, requiring a fully prosthetic body to save Olga’s daughter Sunny, players witness increasingly emotional scenes that play on nostalgia and knowledge of the series’ characters.

When Snake reunites with Eva—initially hiding under the alias “Big Mama”—she recounts Big Boss’s past. After finally meeting his mother, Snake loses her again while trying to protect what were believed to be Big Boss’s remains, later revealed to be Solidus Snake’s. Ocelot seizes control of the Sons of the Patriots system, unleashing absolute chaos among military forces, and Snake is severely burned during the event while attempting to shield Eva, who tries to reach what she believes are Big Boss’s remains.

Guns of the Patriots consistently delivers a narrative of loss and suffering for its characters. Even Otacon, who has lost every woman he has loved—including his young sister shortly after reuniting with her—falls for Dr Hunter, who briefly travels with them, only to lose her as well when she is killed by the still-living Vamp. Naomi dies in the same place as her adoptive brother Frank Jaeger—Gray Fox—in *Metal Gear Solid*, ending Vamp’s life as well through a nanomachine injection that had sustained both of them.

The Shadow Moses confrontation occurs where Ocelot plans to destroy the Patriots' AI, requiring a weapon attached to Metal Gear Rex old enough not to be controlled by the Sons of the Patriots system. This sequence evokes memories of Snake's past missions for both the character and the players. Before reaching the area, Snake experiences a dream sequence from Shadow Moses, during which players can even control him in a section of *Metal Gear Solid* embedded within *Guns of the Patriots*.

Upon waking and visiting the snow-covered island, elements of the original 1998 *Metal Gear Solid* soundtrack play as the player progresses. Various flashbacks, in audio and visual form, evoke Snake's memories of the location. Even the encounter with Beauty and the Beast member Crying Wolf is a tribute to Snake's sniper duel against Sniper Wolf years earlier, in a snowy battlefield.

Solid —Old— Snake back on Shadow Moses island

Ocelot escapes the area, taking control of a new version of the Arsenal Gear from *Metal Gear Solid 2*, which will be named almost identically to the original fortress city from the first *Metal Gear*: Outer Haven, instead of Outer Heaven, and functions as a true floating fortress. This location hosts one of the most emotional scenes in the entire saga, with tension heightened by players sharing the spotlight alongside Snake.

At one point in this final mission, Snake must traverse a corridor containing a device that emits microwaves. This task requires the player to repeatedly press the forward button. Exhausted and severely burned, Snake crawls painfully, while Otacon provides words of encouragement over the radio. Players must continue pressing the action button repeatedly, as Snake progresses slowly—if they stop, he will die. At the end of the tunnel, the final confrontation with Ocelot awaits, following some cinematic sequences. Once again, this sequence is a masterclass in nostalgia.

At the start of the battle, presented in a side-on perspective reminiscent of Solid Snake versus Liquid in *Metal Gear Solid*, cinematic scenes are interspersed with moments in which players control Snake. During the final duel, Ocelot initially appears as “Liquid Ocelot”, but this will change, as will Snake’s designation, eventually displaying as “Revolver Ocelot” with a health bar reminiscent of earlier Metal Gear games. As the player depletes his health, various iconic tracks from the franchise will play, including Cynthia Harrell’s *Snake Eater*, the main theme of *Metal Gear Solid 3*.

It is revealed that Ocelot had replaced Liquid’s arm with a prosthetic, and that the entire theatre of Liquid’s possession was created through self-induced hypnotic therapy, designed to deceive the Patriots. At the conclusion of the fight, Ocelot regains his memories, breaking the hypnosis, which also frees him from the mission and the control he had imposed on himself.

Final showdown between Solid Snake and Revolver Ocelot. During the fight, Ocelot is referred to simply as “Ocelot,” without the “Revolver” nickname he would later acquire after 1964. Snake is called by his father’s codename from *Metal Gear Solid 3*, “Naked Snake,” and even the health bars for both characters use the same design as in that game.

As we gain ground, Ocelot gradually sheds the persona of Liquid Snake, which he had self-implanted through hypnosis, and begins reclaiming his memories as Revolver Ocelot. When we finally defeat him, he performs his signature gesture from *Metal Gear Solid 3* while uttering the words, “You’re Pretty Good”—the same phrase he heard from Big Boss during their first encounter.

Metal Gear Solid 4: Guns of the Patriots continues to feel like an epic farewell to the entire cast of characters. This is seen again at Meryl’s wedding, after Ocelot’s defeat and the game’s conclusion, where Meryl, Campbell, and Snake’s friends are reunited—one of the few genuinely heartwarming moments after so much sorrow. Meanwhile, Old Snake visits the cemetery where The Boss is buried, and there he has a final encounter with his father, Big Boss, who is still alive. After an initial confrontation, father and son reconcile, with Big Boss expressing pride in Snake and, moments before dying—the virus Snake carries also claims Big Boss, who remained in good health despite his age—pleading with him to leave the fight behind.

Big Boss reveals the true story between him and Major Zero, who is now in a vegetative state. Big Boss ends Zero's life by disconnecting him from life support. With Big Boss's death, the Patriots are finally eliminated, freeing Snake and the others from their control. It is a father-and-son reunion reminiscent of the unforgettable ending of *Metal Gear Solid 3*, though this time, it is Solid who weeps over his father's body, once his adversary.

John —Big Boss— embraces his son David —Snake—, and then asks him to 'let it go,' referring to their past as enemies. A heartfelt moment between two characters who have only known violence and death throughout their lives.

With this ending, delivering an emotional impact never before seen in an action video game at the time, and providing a lesson in how a video game can aspire to storytelling as complex, deep, and dense as a series of novels or a film, Hideo Kojima bid farewell to Solid Snake, who shares one last cigar with his father before Big Boss dies, letting slip his final words: “This is Good, Isn’t it?”, perhaps, also as a nod to players themselves.

Sources

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